

Improving Social Media Information Extraction using Multitask Multidataset Learning

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MDMT MetaCorpus

Task	# data	Score
Text classification		
Sentiment	6	~68%
Abusive	2	80-84%
Uncertainty	2	39-85%
Sequence Tagging		
PoS Tagging	7	~90%
Chunking	1	~88%
NER	10	50-89%
Supersense tagging	2	42-59%

- **Classification:** 180K posts
- **Tagging:** 67K posts
- SoTA performance on most datasets

Model

Single task single dataset

(A)

Single task multi-dataset

(B)

Multi-dataset multi-task

(C)

Label Embeddings

SocialMediaIE – Open source library for social media information extraction

- Open Source - <https://github.com/socialmediaie/SocialMediaIE>
- Based on Elmo language model + PyTorch + AllenNLP
- Training and Inference API for batch and web-based inference
- Pre-trained multi-dataset multi-task models
- Aimed at inference focused use-cases which require using efficient and accurate models

